

Effect of Matrix and Stacking Sequence on Delamination Damage in Notched Composite Laminates

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Abstract

The damage processes of the notched composite laminates with different matrices and different stacking sequences during tension-compression fatigue loading have been investigated. The effect of the matrix performance and the stacking sequence on the delamination damage in the laminates is described in this paper.

1. Introduction

Various investigators have studied damage of notched laminates. At present there is no effective method to determine stress distribution in the notched laminates. The damage mechanisms are not yet well understood. This paper describes the effect of different epoxy matrices and different stacking sequences on delamination damage in the laminates with a central hole.

2. Experimental Procedure

Laminates 16 plies thick were fabricated with T300/648, T300/634 and T300/9140 graphite/epoxy prepregs. Two different stacking sequences were selected:

Type A, $\{0_2/+45/0_2/-45/0/90\}_s$

Type B, $\{0_2/90/0_2/+45/0/-45\}_s$

The gauge section of the specimens with a central hole of 10mm diameter was 60mm long by 40mm wide. Fatigue tests were conducted in a servo-hydraulic testing machine. The stress ratio was $R=-1$ and load frequencies were 5 and 10 Hz. Fatigue tests were performed at different stress levels: 460, 400, 350, 250 or 200 MPa. Penetrant enhanced x-ray radiography and ultrasonic C-scanning examination were used at a proper time in testing.

3. Results and Discussion

Fig.1 shows the typical fatigue damage of three kinds of laminates. The high stress gradient at the hole edge results in two longitudinal splits in 0° plies, and the splits lead to the local additional shear stresses between 0° and 45° plies. Three laminates subjected to T-C cyclic load all exhibit delaminations. The shape of the damage area of type A laminates is two crescents symmetrical about the hole centre, but that of type B is an approximate rectangle symmetrical about the load axis. Ultrasonic C-scanning examination shows that the delaminations of type A laminates are at $0_2/-45$ interfaces and that of type B laminates are at $0_2/+45$ and $0/-45$ interfaces. However, the damage growth rates for three kinds of laminates are very different.

The interlaminar stress distribution at the hole edge of type A laminates calculated by a simple method is completely different from that of type B (Fig.2 and Fig.3). For

type A laminates the high interlaminar normal stresses only occur at $\theta = 110^\circ$ and 290° of the interfaces adjacent to -45° plies, and in these positions the interlaminar shear stresses at $0_2/-45$ interfaces are much higher than that at $-45/0$ interfaces. Therefore, the damage of laminates initiates in these positions and the delaminations develop mainly at $0_2/-45$ interfaces. For type B laminates at $\theta = 70^\circ$, 110° , 250° and 290° around the hole at $0_2/-45$, $0_2/+45$ and $+45/0$ interfaces the high interlaminar normal stresses and shear stresses are present, and the shear stresses at $0_2/+45$ interfaces are the highest, so that delaminations develop mainly at $0_2/+45$ interfaces. Fig. 4 shows the initiation of delamination for two types of laminates with ultrasonic C-scanning examination. The observation agrees with the above discussion qualitatively.

4. Conclusions

- (1) The damage of the notched laminates under T-C cyclic load results from the additional interlaminar shear stress caused by the longitudinal splits and the interlaminar peeling stress and shear stress at the hole edge. The stacking sequence of laminates has great influence on damage position and damage growth.
- (2) In the case of T-C cyclic load, the interlaminar peeling stress is very important in causing damage for the notched laminates. The laminates for three investigated matrices delaminated inevitably. Different toughnesses of the matrices lead to obvious difference in the damage growth rate of the laminates. Improving the peeling resistance of the matrix material may postpone the initiation and growth of the laminate damage.

Fig. 1 Fatigue damage of different notched laminates.

- (a) 648-A, $\sigma_a = 250$ MPa, $N = 5.8 \times 10^3$;
- (b) 648-B, $\sigma_a = 250$ MPa, $N = 7.8 \times 10^3$;
- (c) 634-A, $\sigma_a = 250$ MPa, $N = 1.1 \times 10^5$;
- (d) 634-B, $\sigma_a = 250$ MPa, $N = 1.1 \times 10^5$;
- (e) 914C-A, $\sigma_a = 350$ MPa, $N = 1.2 \times 10^4$;
- (f) 914C-B, $\sigma_a = 350$ MPa, $N = 2.3 \times 10^4$.

Fig. 2 Interlaminar stress distribution at the hole edge of type A T300/914C laminate.

Fig. 3 Interlaminar stress distribution at the hole edge of type B T300/914C laminate.

Fig. 4 Delamination initiation positions of two types of notched T300/914C laminates.